

2016-08-03
Fig. 1 GFP control

2016-08-03
Fig. 2 GFP control

2016-08-03
Fig. 1+PV

2016-08-03
Fig. 2+PV

2016-08-03
Fig. 4+PV

2016-08-03
Fig. 1-PV

2016-08-03
Fig. 2-PV

2016-08-04
Fig. 1 control

2016-08-04
Fig. 2 control

2016-08-04
Fig. 3 control

2016-08-04
Fig. 4 control

2016-08-04
Fig. 1+PV

2016-08-04
Fig. 2+PV

2016-08-04
Fig. 4+PV

2016-08-04
Fig. 1-PV

2016-08-04
Fig. 2-PV

2016-08-04
Fig. 3-PV

2016-08-04
Fig. 4-PV

12.08.2016

13.08.2016

2016-08-12
Fig. 1 control

2016-08-12
Fig. 2 control

2016-08-12
Fig. 3 control

2016-08-12
Fig. 4 control

2016-08-12
Fig. 1 +PV

2016-08-12
Fig.2 +PV

2016-08-12
Fig. 3 +PV

2016-08-12
Fig. 4 +PV

2016-08-12
Fig. 1 -PV

2016-08-12
Fig.2 -PV

2016-08-12
Fig. 3 -PV

2016-08-12
Fig. 4 -PV

13-08-2016

2016-08-13
Fig. 1 control

2016-08-13
Fig.2 control

2016-08-13
Fig. 3 control

2016-08-13
Fig. 4 control

2016-08-13
Fig. 1 +PV

2016-08-13
Fig.2 +PV

2016-08-13
Fig. 3 +PV

2016-08-13
Fig. 4 +PV

2016-08-13
Fig. 1 -PV

2016-08-13
Fig.2 -PV

2016-08-13
Fig. 3 -PV

2016-08-13
Fig. 4 -PV

